

**REVIEW: ROMANIAN ACADEMY, BANAT
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The Applied Social Sciences series, published by David Press Print Publishing House in Timișoara, in 2024, represents the third volume of *Banat Encyclopedia*, a vast work that aims to provide as much detailed information as possible, in seemingly divergent fields, such as philosophy, sociology, psychology, pedagogy, social assistance, communication, law, anthropology etc., all of which have their roots in the often Sisyphean effort to decipher the mysteries of man, inclusively the micro and macro social relations. Such a synthesis work aims at the ambitious objective "of improving the global perception of this province about which too little is still known and about which theories and opinions are circulating that are difficult, if not impossible, to accept" (Crișu Dascălu, Introduction, pg. 5). The book, edited by Romanian Academy, is, first, an exceptional work of highlighting the contributions of great personalities,

that originated in Banat Region, in the development of the field of Social Studies in Romania. Secondly, the volume is a model of interdisciplinary collaboration between Romanian experts, professors, researchers and practitioners from different fields of study (education sciences, sociology, philology etc), under the magistral coordination of Romanian Academy, presenting an original, comprehensive and informative view of the development of social studies in the last century, despite numerous difficulties and obstacles. Thirdly, the collective work is, in the same time, a clear statement of the relevance of democratic European values and principles, that are guiding the field of social sciences in Romania. The *Banat Encyclopedia* subtly let us understand the importance of cultural regional bridges between Banat and other Romanian regions, such as Oltenia (in fact, almost surprisingly, many of the personalities described in the book originate or have strong cultural and educational connections with Oltenia Region). It is interesting to note that some personalities who have established themselves in the field of applied social sciences in Banat (Timișoara) or in southwestern Romania are born in Oltenia and culturally linked to this province, such as Dolj county (such as Professor Ștefan Buzărnescu, Professor Constantin Strungă, Professor Dorel Ungureanu, Professor Alin Gavreliuc, Professor Gabriel Mugurel Dragomir) or Gorj county (Professor Adrian Gorun, Professor Ion Hirghiduș).

We appreciate that many of the academic portraits included in the book can serve as models for the future generations of teachers, researchers and scientists, especially in times of great social and political transformation. The collective work is also a statement of the importance of intercultural cooperation between different nationalities and ethnicities that are coexisting in the Banat Region and their shared respect of peace, human rights, freedom. In conclusion, the *Banat Encyclopedia*, coordinated by Romanian Academy, is a much needed

book, that reflects the cultural and educational identity of one of the most important Romanian regions. The exceptional hard work of the volume coordinators helps us better understand the state of the art in the field of social sciences, which is a collective effort many times not wholly understood without a careful intercultural and interdisciplinary analysis of the core personalities that had a substantial contribution in this field.